

HIGH PRESSURE INFILTRATION CASTING AND LASER PROCESSING OF SiCw/Al COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Discontinuously reinforced aluminum composites are very attractive for many structural components requiring high specific stiffness, wear resistance, or high thermal conductivity. We have developed novel techniques to produce silicon carbide whisker preforms which are subsequently infiltrated with molten aluminum alloys, using the high pressure infiltration casting (HiPIC). Secondary processing operations such as cutting and joining are usually required to create components from the composites. Unfortunately, secondary processing techniques, such as cutting and joining are not well developed. Conventional machining techniques are hampered by rapid tool degradation due to the inherently high wear resistance of the composites. Fusion joining techniques are often hampered by interactions between the matrix and the reinforcement material. Laser processing, however, can offer many advantages over conventional techniques. In this investigation, we studied laser cutting and laser beam welding of a commercially available 6061/SiC/20w (fabricated by powder metallurgy hot pressing, and extruded) and the HiPIC composites using a 1.5 kW CO₂ laser. Laser beam welding experimentation was primarily aimed at suppressing the formation of aluminum carbide in the fusion zone of the composites. Additions of titanium and zirconium to the weld to suppress the formation of aluminum carbide.

Keywords: Metal matrix composites, casting, infiltration, laser, cutting, welding, joining, silicon carbide whisker, aluminum, preform, fabrication, pressure casting, high pressure infiltration casting.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites using particulate or whisker reinforcement are generally isotropic and less costly in comparison with continuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs). As a result, the discontinuously reinforced aluminum (DRA) composites are attractive for commercial applications. In addition, whisker reinforced composites offer high resistance to creep and higher use temperatures [1-3]. Commercialization of DRA composites requires effective deformation processing (rolling, forging, or extrusion) to develop improved properties. Production of useful shapes will also require, at least to some extent, secondary processing such as machining and joining, which are yet not established for the composites. Ceramic reinforcement materials have high hardness and as a result conventional machining is very difficult. In order to effectively machine these materials, expensive diamond or cubic boron nitride cutting tools must be used. The high cost of these tools makes conventional machining impractical. The problems of the

conventional machining of metal matrix composites can be eliminated by near net shape manufacturing [4-7] or by non-contact machining techniques such as laser processing [8] and abrasive waterjet cutting [9].

High pressure infiltration casting (HiPIC) is a fabrication process in which a reinforcement preform is rapidly infiltrated with a molten metal under a high pressure [4-7]. Immediately upon the completion of infiltration, the metal solidifies instantaneously followed by fast cooling of the composite under the imposed high pressure. Colloidal silica is generally used in the preform fabrication process in order to provide mechanical stability to the preform. The silica remains in the preform and may react with the matrix metal during the processing. The reaction products, such as Mg_2Si and spinels may cause matrix embrittlement and adversely affect the mechanical properties of the composites [10].

As regards the secondary processing of the composites, lasers offer non-traditional techniques for both machining and joining a wide variety of materials including metal matrix composites [11]. Both laser cutting and laser beam welding involve the use of a focused laser beam to cause melting of the material. An assist gas is applied coaxial to the beam to discharge the molten metal from the cut, in the case of laser cutting. In contrast, the molten metal solidifies under an inert shielding gas, in the case of laser beam welding. The shielding gas prevents the formation of unwanted reactions and gas absorption. However, in the past laser processing of silicon carbide reinforced aluminum composites has been hampered due to the following chemical reaction between the molten aluminum and silicon carbide:

The formation of brittle aluminum carbide platelets reduces the strength of the weld. Further degradation of the weld takes place due to the dissolution of aluminum carbide in aqueous and moist environments. It has also been shown that the formation of aluminum carbide leads to a substantial increase in the viscosity of the melt. This makes it difficult to cast MMCs such as A356/SiCp and A357/SiCp into net shapes [12]. The use of aluminum alloys containing relatively high amounts of silicon is one of the most commonly used methods for eliminating the formation of aluminum carbide during molten metal fabrication techniques. Since the formation of aluminum carbide is inhibited by the high silicon content and a relatively low melt superheat, the fusion joining of these materials is possible if the weld pool temperature is kept below that at which aluminum carbide begins to form [13]. In addition to chemical reactions, several other factors may affect the quality of the weld. For example, the reinforcement materials generally do not melt or dissolve and may segregate in the weld during the laser processing. Another complication is the increased viscosity of the molten pool due to the presence of the reinforcement. This can lead to a sluggish weld pool and incomplete joining [11]. Also, the fabrication processes can have a significant effect on the microstructure of the weld; MMCs produced by powder metallurgy techniques are often subject to the formation of porosity in the fusion zone and heat affected zone (HAZ). The porosity is caused by the presence of hydrogen associated with the oxides on the surface of the metal powder. Upon melting, the adsorbed hydrogen coalesces and forms pores in the weld [14].

In this investigation our objectives were two-fold: a) develop silicon carbide whisker preforms without the use of a silica binder and subsequently infiltrate to fabricate MMCs, b) evaluate the feasibility of the laser cutting and laser beam welding of the whisker reinforced composites.

2. PREFORM DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Tape Casting

Silicon carbide whiskers used for the preform development have a diameter of 0.05-0.2 μm and a length of 10-40 μm . An organic binder (B-73305, Palomar Metoramic Sciences Inc.) and toluene were used with the silicon carbide whiskers to fabricate preforms. The rule of mixtures was used to estimate the amount of silicon carbide whisker and the organic binder necessary to obtain

the desired fiber volume fraction in the preforms. The silicon carbide whisker and binder were measured and placed into a milling jar containing aluminum oxide milling balls. Toluene was added to the mixture to obtain a slurry viscosity suitable for tape casting. The formulations for the three volume fraction slurries are shown in Table 1. When the consistency of the slurry was adjusted, the jar was placed on a ball mill for approximately twenty hours to produce a homogeneous slurry. The slurry was then allowed to rest fifteen minutes prior to tape casting to remove any air entrapped in the slurry. A tape casting machine was used to apply a thin uniform layer of the slurry onto a plastic carrier film. Once dry, the tape was cut into squares (50 mm x 50 mm) and stacked into a lamination die.

Table 1. Slurry formulations for silicon carbide whisker preforms (measurements in grams)

Vf, %	Calculated Values		Actual Values		
	SiCw	Binder	SiCw	Binder	Toluene
20	45.0	251.7	45	253	20
30	74.7	243.5	75	245	42
40	111.4	233.5	111	233	140

2.2. Lamination Cycle

The stack of tape layers is joined and consolidated into "green" laminates by the simultaneous application of heat and pressure. The heat softens the organic binder and the applied pressure bonds the individual layers to give nominal strength. The pressure cycles for 40 volume fraction laminates, along with the average die temperature are shown in Figure 1. The die was rotated every 3 minutes to account for any misalignment in the platens of the lamination press. Once the lamination cycle was complete, the laminates were subjected to a burnout process for the removal of the organic binder.

Figure 1. Time and temperature plot for lamination of tape layers into a single preform.

2.3. Binder Burnout

A heating cycle to remove the organic binder from the preforms was developed using the manufacturers' specifications for binder decomposition. The cycle, shown in Figure 2, is designed to allow the gaseous decomposition products to escape without damaging the preform. Burnout was completed in air with an electric furnace employing a programmable temperature controller. Figure 3 is an SEM micrograph of the burnout preform which shows that the organic binder has been removed completely by the decomposition cycle.

Figure 2. Temperature cycle used to remove organic binder from the whisker preforms.

Figure 3. SEM micrograph of the silicon carbide whisker preform which shows the results of the decomposition cycle shown in Figure 2.

3. HIGH PRESSURE INFILTRATION CASTING

The developed preforms were infiltrated with aluminum alloy A356 by the high pressure infiltration casting. The required amount of aluminum was melted in a graphite crucible with a graphite cover. The preform was heated outside the die. Upon placing the preheated preform in the die, the molten aluminum was poured immediately onto the preform. The punch was inserted into the die and the pressure was applied to a maximum of 100 MPa. This pressure was maintained for 45 seconds to ensure an instantaneous solidification following the infiltration. The high pressure also results in fast cooling of the composite.

3.1. Microstructure of the Cast Composites

The microstructure of the fabricated composites is fairly uniform and almost free from porosity and other defects. Optical micrographs of the fabricated A356/SiC/40w composite are shown in Figure 4a and 4b. Figure 4a shows the planar microstructure of the material, revealing a uniform microstructure and few defects (pores). Figure 4b exhibits individual tape layers in the laminate.

Figure 4a. Optical micrograph (planar) of the A356/SiC/40w composite produced by HiPIC.

Figure 4b. Optical micrograph of the through-the-thickness cross section of the A356/SiC/40w composite produced by HiPIC.

4. LASER PROCESSING

The fabricated composites with volume fraction of 20, 30, and 40 percent and a wrought 6061/SiC/20w composite [obtained from ACMC (Greer, SC)] were used to study the feasibility of laser processing. A Coherent General EFA 51, 1.5 kW, enhanced fast axial flow, CO₂ gas laser, with continuous wave (CW) and pulsed TEM₀₀ mode capability was used during the investigation. A focal arrangement utilizing a 6.35 mm lens produced a focused spot size of 120 μm at an output wavelength of 10.6 μm, in the infrared range. Shielding or assist gas was provided coaxial to the beam, and a computer controlled micropositioning system was employed to manipulate the test specimens during the laser processing. The experimental arrangement used for the laser cutting and laser beam welding is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Experimental configuration for laser cutting and laser beam welding.

The amount of laser energy absorbed by the material is one factor which determines the effectiveness of the laser processing. In general, improved absorptivity results in improved processing efficiency, allowing for deeper penetration and faster processing speeds. Aluminum has relatively high reflectivity which decreases its ability to effectively absorb, or couple with the laser beam. The reinforcement materials commonly used in discontinuously reinforced aluminum composites are aluminum oxide and silicon carbide and they absorb much more energy at 10.6 μm wavelength (see Figure 6). Initial experiments revealed that energy absorbed by the composite materials was greater than the unreinforced aluminum. The improved energy absorption is attributed to the change in reflectivity of the bulk material by the addition of the reinforcement. The rule of mixtures was used to calculate the effective emissivities for the composites (see Table 2).

Figure 6. Emissivities of matrix and reinforcement materials [15,16].

Table 2. Calculated emissivity values for the composites.

Material	Emissivity, %
Al/SiC/40	8.33
Al/SiC/30	6.72
Al/SiC/20	5.11
Aluminum [15]	1.90

4.1. Laser Cutting

Laser cutting of the silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composites was hampered by the formation of aluminum carbide. An aluminum carbide reaction layer was observed on the cut surface of the composites and a significant amount of dross containing aluminum carbide remained attached to the bottom of the cut. This may be due to the potential reaction between the molten aluminum and the silicon carbide whiskers, forming a highly viscous mixture of aluminum carbide and silicon. The assist gas moves the mixture toward the bottom of the cut, but is unable to expel it completely, due to its high viscosity. This results in a thin layer of aluminum carbide on the cut surface and a buildup of aluminum carbide dross at the bottom of the cut. The amount of dross attached to the bottom of the cut can be quite significant; the average height of the dross attached to the bottom of a 2 mm sample of the 6061/SiC/20w composite was 1.25 mm. Several different assist gases, power levels, and travel speeds were used in an attempt to minimize the dross formation. Variation of processing parameters had little effect on the cut quality. The formation of aluminum carbide appears to override the ability to obtain laser cuts with a clean surface.

4.2. Laser Beam Welding

A comparison of the effective emissivities to the penetration depths of a wrought 6061/SiC/20w composite and aluminum alloy 6061 is shown in Figure 7. The effective emissivities agree reasonably well with the weld penetration depths, although the low value for 6061 is due to the lack of sufficient energy density to initiate coupling. Minor effects from processing may occur, however the comparison shows a correlation between the emissivity of the material and the effectiveness of laser processing.

Figure 7. Comparison of the effective emissivity to the weld penetration depth.

The formation of aluminum carbide was expected during the laser beam welding of the composite produced by HiPIC. In addition to the formation of aluminum carbide, another problem was observed. Micrographs of autogenous welds made on HiPIC composites exhibit not only the formation of aluminum carbide in the fusion zone, but also gross porosity in the heat affected zone (see Figure 8). The HAZ porosity is probably due to the hydrogen in solution in the cast composites. The porosity in the HiPIC composites is much greater than that observed in the P/M composite material. Melting during the laser beam welding of the composite results in the evolution and coalescence of the hydrogen, leading to porosity throughout the fusion and heat affected zones.

Figure 8. Laser weld on A356/SiC/30w composite showing gross porosity in the fusion and heat affected zones.

Silicon addition has been successfully used to allow the fusion joining of silicon carbide reinforced aluminum composites [13]. Suppression of the formation of aluminum carbide can be achieved by thermodynamic considerations other than silicon additions. Comparison of free energy of formation data indicate that several metallic carbides are more thermodynamically favorable than aluminum carbide. In particular, titanium and zirconium carbides show the most promise in

eliminating the formation of aluminum carbide based on free energy change, as shown in Figure 9. Titanium carbide and zirconium carbide are chemically stable compounds and are not subject to dissolution in water. Experimentation of laser welds made with commercially pure titanium additions shows that the formation of aluminum carbide has been suppressed in the 6061/SiC/20w composite. Instead of large platelets of aluminum carbide, very fine dendritic structures are found in the fusion zone, as shown in Figure 10. These dendrites are extremely small (1-5 μm) and evenly dispersed throughout the fusion zone. Electron microprobe analysis indicates that the dendrites consist of only titanium and carbon, which strongly suggests that they are titanium carbide. Initial analysis of the welds made with zirconium additions shows similar results.

Figure 9. Free energy of formation for various metallic carbides as a function of temperature.

Figure 10. SEM micrograph of titanium carbide dendrites in the fusion zone of 6061/SiC/20w plates butt welded using titanium addition.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Silicon carbide whisker preforms have been developed for fabricating metal matrix composites. The preforms do not contain silica binder, yet they have adequate strength. The preforms are not compressed or damaged during the high pressure infiltration casting. The fabricated composites are thoroughly infiltrated and have few pores. Experimental parameters have been established for the laser cutting and laser beam welding of the cast aluminum composites and a wrought aluminum composite. Additions of titanium and zirconium to the weld suppress the formation of aluminum carbide.

REFERENCES

1. Bhagat, R.B., and House, M.B., "Elevated Temperature Mechanical Properties of Silicon Carbide Reinforced Aluminum Matrix Composites", *Materials Science and Engineering*, Vol. A144, 1991, pp. 319-326.
2. House, M.B., Meinert, K.C., Bhagat, R.B., "The Aging Response and Creep of DRA Composites", *JOM*, August 1991, pp. 24-28.
3. Bhagat, R.B., Amateau, M.F., House, M.B., Meinert, K.C., Nisson, P., "Elevated Temperature Mechanical Properties of Silicon Carbide Reinforced Aluminum Matrix Composites", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No. 11, 1992, pp. 1578-1593.
4. Bhagat, R.B., "High Pressure Infiltration Casting: Manufacturing Net Shape Composites with a Unique Interface", *Materials Science and Engineering*, Vol. A144, 1991, pp. 243-251.
5. Canumalla, S., Dynan, S.D., Bhagat, R.B., Conway, J.C., Green, D.G., Pangborn, R.N., and Tittman, B.R., "In-Process Sensing During the Casting of Discontinuous Fiber Reinforced Aluminum Composites", *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference of Composite Materials*.
6. Bhagat, R.B., "Casting Fiber Reinforced Metal Matrix Composites", In: *Treatise on Materials Science and Technology, Volume 32: Metal Matrix Composites: Processing and Interfaces*, eds. R. Arsenault and R. Everett, Academic Press, Orlando, FL, 1991, pp. 43-82.
7. Bhagat, R.B., Amateau, M.F., Conway, J.C., Paulick, J.M., Chisholm, J.M., and Seidensticker, D.G., "Squeeze Cast Metal Matrix Composites: Evaluation of Their Strength, Damping Capacity and Corrosion Resistance", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 23, No. 9, 1989, pp. 961-975.
8. Simpson, G.P., and Culkin, T.J., "Laser Cutting", *ASM Metals Handbook, 9th Edition, Volume 16: Machining*, pp. 735-742.
9. Sylvia, J.G., "Abrasive Waterjet Cutting", *ASM Metals Handbook, 9th Edition, Volume 16: Machining*, pp. 743-755.
10. Baty, D.L., Price, J.P., and Coleman, B.G., "Selective Properties of Aluminum Alloys Reinforced with Aluminum-Silica Fibers", Technical Paper EM87-573, Society of Manufacturing Engineers, Dearborn, MI, 1987.
11. Martukanitz, R.P., and Bhagat, R.B., 1992, "Laser Processing of Discontinuously Reinforced Aluminum Matrix Composites", *The Metal Science of Joining*, Cieslak, M.J., Prerpezko, J.H., Kang, S., and Glicksman, M.E., eds., TMS, pp. 241-248.
12. Schuster, David M., Skibo, Michael D., Hoover, William R., "Production and Semi-Fabrication of an Aluminum Composite Material: Extrusion and Casting Considerations", *Light Metal Age*, February 1989, pp. 15-19.
13. Arc Welding Guidelines, Duralcan, 1991.
14. Martukanitz, R. P., and Michnuk, P.R., 1982, "Sources of Porosity in Gas Metal Arc Welding of Aluminum", *Trends in Welding Research in the United States*, David, S. A., ed., ASM International, pp. 315-330.
15. Duley, W.W., *Laser Processing and Analysis of Materials*, 1983, p. 71.
16. Moses, A.J., *Optical Properties of Materials: Handbook of Electronic Materials*, Vol. 1, 1971, pp. 4-5, 72-73.